

PROBLEMS OF TRAINING MOBILE NETWORK OPERATORS IN THE INTRODUCTION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada uyali aloqa tarmoqlarining operatorlarini o‘qitishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari keltirilgan. Uyali aloqa tarmoqlarining operatorlarini o‘qitishda qo‘llaniladigan zamonaviy texnologiyalar tahlil qilingan. Uyali aloqa tarmoqlarining texnologiyalari qo‘llaniladigan usul va algoritmlar to‘liq keltirilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены научно-теоретические основы использования цифровых технологий в обучении операторов мобильной связи. Проанализированы современные технологии, используемые при обучении операторов сотовой связи. Полностью представлены методы и алгоритмы, используемые в технологиях сетей сотовой связи.

Annotation. This article presents the scientific theoretical basis of the use of digital technologies in the training of mobile network operators. The modern technologies used in the training of cellular network operators are analyzed. The methods and algorithms used in the technologies of cellular communication networks are fully presented.

Kalit so‘zlar. *Mobil tarmoqlar, tarmoq operatorlari, raqamlashtirish, Texnologiya, 2G texnologiya, 3D texnologiya tarmoq infratuzilmasi, aloqa kompaniyalari.*

Ключевые слова. *Мобильные сети, операторы тарифов, Цифролизации, Технология, технология 2G, технология 3D, тармок инфраструктура сети, сотовые компания.*

Keywords. *Mobile networks, tariff operators, Digitalization, Technology, 2G technology, 3D technology, tarmok infrastructure networks, mobil companies.*

Introduction

In this paper we argue that the development of multinational mobile network operators can be usefully divided into three technologically conditioned phases. The first phase, 1990-2010, we refer to as “the rise of the MNOs” and spanned 2G and 3G wireless technologies. Industry boundaries were clear-cut, and, given their FSAs, the MNOs dominated their industry throughout this phase. Internationalization involved exploitation of these FSAs across geographies in a “replication” strategy resulting in locally adapted multi-domestic operations dependent on the parent company capabilities. Voice and messaging were the primary sources of income.

The main part

The launch of 4G and mobile internet connectivity in 2010 was ostensibly another boost for MNOs and the wider mobile telecom ecosystem. By 2015 the mobile telecom ecosystem generated over US\$3.1tn of economic value-added, equivalent to 4.2% of the global gross domestic product and provided 17 million jobs directly and a further 15 million jobs indirectly (GSMA, 2016; Dike and Rose, 2017)[1].

However, by around 2015 it was clear that MNO growth was slowing, not only

voice and messaging but also internet connectivity as the worldwide market for mobile approached saturation. One tangible factor was that national regulators, particularly those in developed countries, between 2010 and 2015 augmented competition by increasingly compelling MNOs to share their network infrastructures with *mobile virtual network operator (MVNOs)*, causing prices for mobile services to decline (Fierce Wireless, 2015). Between 2015 and 2020, the combined market capitalization of the wider European telecoms sector buckled. In 2020, it was 75% of what it was in 2000 (Financial Times, 2020a). The outcome was that heavy debt burdens became prevalent across many of the players in the industry with their market capitalizations dwarfed by their borrowings (Financial Times, 2020b)[2]. Telefonica was particularly indebted and in addition to pulling out of South America except for Brazil, it sought to consolidate its operations by merging its UK unit O2 with Liberty Global's Virgin Media in search of efficiencies and financial stability (Financial Times, 2020a). Even the debt-free MNO Telenor prioritized the pursuit of efficiencies in the context of increasingly challenging markets (Elter et al., 2020).

Thus, as Telenor and MNOs in general enter the 5G era, what remained in terms of FSAs is their ability to orchestrate external actors. However, we argue that because connectivity provision and the need to retain operation licenses had necessitated local market presence, Telenor possessed significantly more local insidership than the global digital firms. Further, we will argue that local insidership could constitute an FSA in the 5G era. Our argument builds on insights in the work of Brouthers et al. (2016) (see also Dasi et al., 2019) that in an era when national governments are increasingly seeking to control, curtail and even preclude global digital firms from their markets, local insidership could be of substantial long-term value. While to date there is no firm evidence to support this notion there are indications that global digital firms are being subjected to increasing levels of regulatory friction across markets. To take two examples from very different markets. In the EU, regulators argue that the world's largest online platforms such as Google and Amazon have gained "gatekeeper status" and are using the control they have of marketplaces where they also sell their own products and services to potentially disadvantage smaller, local competitors[3]. The EU's prospective Digital Services Act aims at tackling "the entrenched advantages" enjoyed by "Big Tech" by forcing the likes of Google and Amazon to share customer data collected on their platforms with business users active in the same commercial sphere (Financial Times, 2020c). The Act is designed "to ensure a level playing field for all digital companies, regardless of their size by lay(ing) down clear rules for big platforms - a list of 'dos' and 'don'ts' - which aim to stop them from imposing unfair conditions on (small, digital) businesses" (European Parliament News, 2021)[5]. In Pakistan, the authorities have sought to regulate the information and communication technology landscape in order to exert control over global digital platforms by requiring data localization, i.e. the storage of citizens' data in data centers within Pakistan's border (Malkani, 2020). Introduced in November 2020, this set of "vaguely worded" rules "granted the government broad authorities to pressure companies to restrict access to content and facilitate exceptional access to user data" (Global Network Initiative, 2021). Companies that fail to comply could be subject

to fines of up to 500 million rupees (over US \$3 million). Main FSAs and FSARs required for competitive B2B positioning. For MNOs to succeed with the transition to advanced IoT and 5G services, four sets of FSAs are seminal[6].

The first set of FSAs involves the upgrading of the 5G network with edge computing and provision of APIs in order to utilize 5G features. For MNOs to provide advanced 5G services, all parts of the network from radio transmission to the core network requires a fundamental upgrading. This upgrading span network slicing that enables network priority, which is an end-to-end, secured, and customized network for particular business-critical solutions. It also involves access to network function virtualization (NFV), a technology that allows software applications to access features of the 5G network through APIs. Most MNOs including Telenor are upgrading the 5G network starting with the radio network to allow increased speed, capacity, and the potential for significantly less lag time. For the case of Norway, Telenor expects all parts of the network to have been upgraded by 2023[7].

The second set of FSAs comprises the development of a portal that facilitates the exposure of APIs to partners. To stimulate 5G service innovation, the network infrastructure vendors such as Ericsson, Nokia and Huawei are promoting the use of APIs to expose 5G network resources (Varnai, 2019). The development of this set of FSAs is underway at MNOs such as Vodafone, Telefonica, Orange, Telia as well as Telenor. Using 4G these MNOs are exposing APIs to various existing platforms through developer portals. This application is set to expand significantly as 5G is adopted[8].

The third set of FSAs involves IoT and AI. 5G supported IoT can be applied across a significant range of applications including smart-factories, smart-buildings, smart-cities, smart-utilities, smart-homes, security and surveillance, agriculture, retail, and health. IoT devices are capable of generating substantial amounts of data in real time with low-latency monitoring provided by artificial intelligence (AI). The challenge for Telenor and MNOs in general is to use their in-house AI competencies to inform the strategic selection of AI resources[9].

The fourth set of FSAs involves possessing advisory and system integration capabilities. Telenor informants report that they are advising customers on how to deploy 5G and IoT technologies. The latter requires system integration FSAs.

An indication of Telenor's development of 5G related FSAs is that its Norwegian business unit is engaged in the co-creation of 5G business solutions in areas such as logistics, fish-farming, Norwegian hospitals, and the Norwegian Armed Forces. To take one example from fish-farming, Telenor is together with its partners developing solutions that enable fish-farmers to identify among vast numbers of individual fish any that are developing early symptoms of disease. These can then be removed from the stock before contaminating other fish.

Conclusion

We have traced the evolution of MNOs in general, and Telenor in particular, from their relatively sudden and swift emergence as suppliers of voice and messaging (2G), followed by internet (3G) and mobile-broadband internet connectivity (4G). During the 4G era (2010-2020), MNOs failed to develop the

required FSAs to monetize the opportunity to become digital service providers. Instead they remained best effort providers of connectivity based on the FSAs developed during the 3G era. The outcome was that mobile broadband internet connectivity was exploited by technology platform companies such as Amazon, Google and Microsoft to develop and launch their digital service offerings and who thereby “skimmed most of the value generated by 4G mobile technology” (Economist, 2022). In terms of internationalization we observe that while MNOs were well suited to rolling out 2G and, more significantly, 3G, to developing, as well as well as developed, economies, by exploiting their FSAs, they lacked the FSAs to exploit 4G. Despite sensing the requirements for new 4G FSAs and seizing elements of these, MNOs as illustrated by Telenor were lacking in the FSARs that would have enabled them to evolve into digital service providers. Consequently, significant value migrated from voice, and messaging to digital services provided by “born globals”.

References

1. Adarkwah, G.K., Malonaes, T.P., 2020. Firm-specific advantages: a comprehensive review with a focus on emerging markets. *Asia Pac. J. Manag.* 1-47.
2. Agrawal, J., Patel, R., Mor, P., Dubey, P., Keller, J.M., 2015. Evolution of mobile communication network: from 1G to 4G. *Int. J. Multidiscip. Curr. Res.* 3, 1100-1103.
3. Akkaraju, L., Waldemar, P., 2021. How 5G and industrial data platforms will transform heavy industry (Reader Forum) 20 August 2021. <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20210820/5g/how-5g-and-industrial-data-platforms-will-transform-heavy-industry-reader-forum> (Accessed 24 August 2021).
4. Alturi, V., Dietz, M., Henke, N., 2017. Competing in a world of sectors without borders. *McKinsey quarterly* July 12, 2017. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/competing-in-a-world-of-sectors-without-borders>.
5. Little, Arthur D., 2019. Telco retail challenges in 2025, what is the end-game? March 2019. <https://www.adlittle.es/en/telco-retail-challenges-2025-what-end-game> (Accessed on 18. January 2021).
6. Baksaas, J.F., 2019. Min historie om Telenor (My history of Telenor). Gyldendal, Oslo.
7. Bartlett, C.A., Ghoshal, S., 1989. *Managing Across Borders: The Transnational Solution*. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA, Boston.
8. Bauer, J.M., 1994. Globalization of telecommunications operators under conditions of asymmetric national regulation. In: *Papers Presented to the Ninth International Telecommunications Society (ITS) on Global Telecommunications Strategies and Technological Changes*, pp. 315-331.
9. Brekke, S., 2020. 5G in the Digital Transformation. Presentation at 3rd Nordic Conference on ICT: 5G for Industry & Society Oslo, 5 November 2020.
10. Brouthers, K.D., Dung Geisser, K., Rothlauf, F., 2016. Explaining the internationalization of Ibusiness firms. *J. Int. Bus. Stud.* 47 (5), 513-534.